

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING PRODUCT PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN REGIONAL SMALL INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: In our article on the topic of foreign experience of increasing the efficiency of production in small industrial enterprises of the region, we present information about the study of foreign experiences and their efficiency in production in small industrial enterprises. The article focuses on such important processes as technological innovations, training of working personnel, improvement of information systems, introduction of investments and external cooperation successfully implemented in foreign countries. It shows how foreign experience can be useful for enterprises, in developing their activities and opening new opportunities.

Keywords: Automation, Technological approaches, Production, Efficiency, Integration, Monitoring, Data analysis, foreign experience, efficiency improvement, regional industry.

One option for increasing the productivity of small industrial enterprises in the region is the use of technological development and innovation. New and modern technologies, such as robotics, IoT (Internet of Things), and automation systems should be used. Analyzes how small industrial enterprises use foreign experience and guidelines for its implementation. This shows the importance of using foreign experience for enterprises and helps them to choose the ways to improve their efficiency.

Production processes are automated and efficiency is increased. For businesses, training and development of their employees can help them manage their production processes more effectively. It plays an important role in improving the field of industry and ensuring the production of quality products. Improving communication between enterprises, improving data sharing and developing work management systems leads to more effective management and optimization of work. Establishing programs to encourage innovation and innovation for industrial enterprises in the region, creating new markets and opportunities for enterprises. By developing infrastructure and communications, such as energy, transportation, and telecommunications infrastructure, needed to increase productivity, businesses can operate more efficiently. This helps to create favorable conditions for enterprises. It is

important to use and cooperate with intercity and international foreign investment in improving the efficiency of small industrial enterprises in the region. This opens up opportunities for businesses to grow and enter new markets.

In the study of foreign experience, it became clear that technological innovation and automation are of great importance. New technologies, such as robotics and IoT (Internet of Things), play a major role in optimizing production processes and increasing efficiency. Good training of working personnel and providing them with new technologies is important in foreign experience. Improvements in worker training and educational environment are necessary for more efficient management of production processes and rapid learning of innovations. Foreign experience has shown that it is of great importance to improve information systems, improve communication and monitor work processes in order to improve application and improve management efficiency. Foreign investment and cooperation are of great importance in the study of foreign experience in improving efficiency in small industrial enterprises of the region. Establishing a business and entering new markets, attracting and supporting foreign investment will help increase efficiency. Foreign experience is important in learning, exporting products to new markets, increasing the quality of products, and increasing the effectiveness of market diversification. This will help create new opportunities for businesses. Abroad experience has shown that it is important to learn, accept and put into practice. Based on good overseas experience and applied best practices, businesses can take practical steps to improve their performance.

It analyzes the processes of increasing the efficiency of production in the economy of foreign countries, how they were successful in practice, the strategies and programs used. Explain the importance of technological innovation and automation in industrial enterprises, how they have been successfully used in foreign countries, their role in increasing efficiency and what are the guidelines for increasing efficiency. Analyzes foreign investments in industrial enterprises, reforms, foreign investments and cooperation between enterprises. The importance of work management and management in foreign countries in increasing the efficiency of production, the best practices from foreign experience, what development in the foreign financial market causes. These literatures contribute to a broad and in-depth analysis of the subject and are used to explain, study and apply foreign experience in the field of product development.

The region explains the foreign experience of improving the efficiency of production in small industrial enterprises, the important guidelines and strategies that can be obtained for enterprises. Successful models and programs, demonstrated in practice in foreign countries, show how they can help improve efficiency in small industrial enterprises. These experiences can be related to areas such as bringing effective innovations and technologies for small enterprises, improving the quality of work management and management, training quality workers, improving information systems and entering markets, entrepreneurship and investments. Foreign experience is important because it provides advice and practical support for small enterprises, creating ample opportunities for their development, entering new markets, exporting their products, and improving efficient production processes.

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